

MODELLING AND OPTIMIZATION ANALYSIS OF COMPOSITE TAPE SPRING

Yang Zhang¹, Hong ling Ye¹, Qing sheng Yang¹

¹Beijing University of Technology, and, zhang-yang@emails.bjut.edu.cn, yehongl@bjut.edu.cn
qsyang@bjut.edu.cn

Keywords: Composite material, Tape spring, Mechanical properties, Optimization

ABSTRACT

To obtain a better composite design of tape spring, an optimization process is given in this paper. A representative unit cell of plain woven composite material is established using TexGen. Through the finite element analysis the equivalent elastic constants are extracted. Based on classic laminate theory the ABD matrix of symmetric ply laminate is derived and assigned to tape spring. The bending moment and strain energy of tape spring made of the foregoing composite materials are investigated. A multi-objective optimization model is established with constraints of critical moment and longitudinal strain. After solved using the modified Non-Dominated Sorting Genetic Algorithm (ASGA-II), the optimal design is obtained and then it is simulated and compared to the optimal solution, results show that there are differences being less than 1%, which indicates the optimal design is accurate.

1 INTRODUCTION

A tape spring, also referred to as carpenter's tape, is a straight strip with a natural curved cross section. The tape spring can be elastically folded and store strain energy. During deployment the stored strain energy is converted into kinetic energy. Once having full deployment, the tape spring will be self-locking due to its stiffness resulting from natural curved section. For the simplicity, repeatability and unique folding properties, tape spring has become common in deployable space structures. Where the unique folding properties are that the mechanical properties is direction dependent. When the direction of bending moment is same as the transverse curvature, this is called positive folding; while if opposite to transverse curvature, this case is reverse folding, as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Schematics of folding.

The mechanical properties are characterised by profiles of moment of tape spring. Wuest [1] and Mansfield [2] firstly introduced analytical developments on tape springs linking the rotation angle and moment responses. More recently, the analytical expressions are developed on tape springs by theoretical derivation [3-6], and it is also expanded to three dimensions, in which the relationships between moment responses and curvatures as well as torsion angle are predicted through a variational approach, meanwhile simulation and experiment verify the developments [7-8].

The classical evaluation of moment with respect to rotation is plotted in Figure 2, it is recalled here and the short descriptions are given. According to the picture, for reverse folding (opposite sense bending), moment increases linearly to a peak with a small rotation, after then moment jumps to a smaller value and remains it approximate constant all the way to full folding. For reverse deploying, the moment follows almost the same path of folding, but the difference is that the snap-back corresponds to a smaller buckling rotation, that is the θ_+^{heel} is less than θ_+^{max} , this phenomenon is called hysteresis which results in the locking of tape spring. The peak in moment curves is critical moment, corresponding to snap through of tape spring and measuring capacity of resisting disturbance at straight configuration. The approximate constant is steady moment, measuring the driving ability. For positive folding(or equal sense folding), similarly the critical and steady moments are used to characterize mechanical properties of tape spring, however, the positive fold is formed through several asymmetrically local deformations, thereby positive folding is considerably slow, there are consequently less pronounced differences between positive folding and deploying.

Figure 2: Moment evaluation with respect to rotation [9].

On the other hand, due to good performances, composite material is introduced into tape spring, the composite tube hinges are closely related to tape spring hinges are investigated with respect to structural design and mechanical properties, using numerical and experimental methods [10-11].

In this paper we particularly investigate the single tape spring made of plane weave composite materials. The representative unit of composite material is established in TexGen4SC [12], software developed based on TexGen [13] which is exploited by University of Nottingham. And then the equivalent elastic constants are calculated through SwiftComp [12]. The classical laminated plate theory evaluates the ABD stiffness of a symmetrically simple layer. Mechanical properties of composite tape spring are investigated and DOE tests are carried out with full factorial design about design variables. Final multi-objective optimization is completed based on response surface methodology and some conclusions are drawn.

2 ELASTIC CONSTANTS AND ABD MATRIX

2.1 Calculation of elastic constants

A tape spring has four parameters: its length L , its thickness t , its subtended angle θ and transverse radius of curvature R . The geometry of tape spring is shown in Figure 3. The initial design is $L=140$ mm, $\theta = 120^\circ$, $t=0.8$ mm, $R=18$ mm. The finite element model is established in ABAQUS, meshed with S4R dealing with large displacement and small strain. Two reference nodes coinciding with the centroids of cross-sections at ends of tape spring are added for defining the boundary conditions. The details of simulation techniques can be seen in our previous work [14].

Figure 3: Geometry of tape spring.

The representative unit cell of plain weave composite material is given in Figure 4. There are two warps and wefts woven with each other. Then the physical parameters as listed in Table 1 are assigned to fibres and yarns. The whole unit cell is meshed with volume element C3D8R, and we export the mesh for SwiftComp to calculate the equivalent elastic constant. The obtain mechanical parameters are $E_1 = E_2 = 25.043\text{GPa}$, $G_{12} = 2.3803\text{GPa}$, $\mu_{12} = \mu_{21} = 0.3267$.

Figure 4: Representative unit cell of plain weave.

linear density of yarn	fibres per yarn	fibre density	diameter of fibre	warp numbers	weft numbers	gap between warp and weft	width of yarn
g/km		g/m^3	μm			mm	mm
276	2400	2.258	5.07	2	2	1.29	0.8

Table 1: Parameters for representative unit cell of plain weave.

2.2 ABD matrix for tape spring

The stress-strain equation can be written as matrix with the form of

$$\begin{bmatrix} \sigma_1 \\ \sigma_2 \\ \tau_{12} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} Q_{11} & Q_{12} & 0 \\ Q_{12} & Q_{22} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & Q_{66} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \varepsilon_1 \\ \varepsilon_2 \\ \gamma_{12} \end{bmatrix} \quad (1)$$

Where, the subscripts 1 and 2 in stress matrix or strain matrix correspond to the fibre direction and perpendicular to fibre direction, respectively. Q_{ij} is called reduced stiffness coefficient and it can be represented using engineering constants with the form of

$$\begin{cases} Q_{11} = \frac{E_1}{1 - \mu_{12}\mu_{21}}, & Q_{22} = \frac{E_2}{1 - \mu_{12}\mu_{21}} \\ Q_{66} = G_{12}, & Q_{12} = \mu_{12}Q_{22} \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

In practical application, fibre direction of composite material isn't all the time corresponding to global coordinate system. To make the Eq. (1) be satisfied in any case, the more general form is given

$$\begin{bmatrix} \sigma_x \\ \sigma_y \\ \tau_{xy} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \bar{Q}_{11} & \bar{Q}_{12} & \bar{Q}_{16} \\ & \bar{Q}_{22} & \bar{Q}_{26} \\ \text{sym.} & & \bar{Q}_{66} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \varepsilon_x \\ \varepsilon_y \\ \gamma_{xy} \end{bmatrix} \quad (3)$$

Where, the transformed stiffness coefficient \bar{Q}_{ij} is controlled by Eq. (4), in which $m = \cos \theta$, $n = \sin \theta$, and θ is angle of rotating global x-axis to fibre direction.

$$\begin{cases} \bar{Q}_{11} = m^4 Q_{11} + 2m^2 n^2 (Q_{12} + 2Q_{66}) + n^4 Q_{22} \\ \bar{Q}_{12} = m^2 n^2 (Q_{11} + Q_{22} - 4Q_{66}) + (m^4 + n^4) Q_{12} \\ \bar{Q}_{22} = n^4 Q_{11} + 2m^2 n^2 (Q_{12} + 2Q_{66}) + m^4 Q_{22} \\ \bar{Q}_{16} = m^3 n (Q_{11} - Q_{12}) + mn^3 (Q_{12} - Q_{22}) - 2mn(m^2 - n^2) Q_{66} \\ \bar{Q}_{26} = mn^3 (Q_{11} - Q_{12}) + m^3 n (Q_{12} - Q_{22}) + 2mn(m^2 - n^2) Q_{66} \\ \bar{Q}_{66} = m^2 n^2 (Q_{11} + Q_{22} - 2Q_{12} - 2Q_{66}) + (m^4 + n^4) Q_{66} \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

According to deformation assumption of thin plate, the section of deformed thin plate stays a plane, thus based on laminated plate theory, the constitutive relation of laminated plate is written as Eq. (5). N in the equation is resultant force matrix in unit width and M represent resultant moment matrix in unit width.

$$\begin{Bmatrix} N \\ M \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} A & B \\ B & D \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \varepsilon^0 \\ K \end{Bmatrix} \quad (5)$$

The symmetric layers with $[0/90]_s$ is applied to tape spring, therefore all components of stiffness matrix B are equal to zero. Meanwhile stiffness matrixes A and D are calculated by Eq. (6) and Eq. (7), in which t_k is thickness of single layer, and the coordinate of middle surface of k th player is \bar{z}_k , and \bar{z}_k is given by $\bar{z}_k = (z_{k-1} + z_k)/2$.

$$A_{ij} = \sum_{k=1}^n t_k (\bar{Q}_{ij})_k \quad (6)$$

$$D_{ij} = \sum_{k=1}^n \left[t_k (\bar{z}_k)^2 + \frac{1}{12} (t_k)^3 \right] \cdot (\bar{Q}_{ij})_k \quad (7)$$

Let us assume that thickness of tape spring is t , therefore t_k is $t_k = t/4$. Due to symmetry, the stiffness coefficients \bar{Q}_{16} and \bar{Q}_{26} are equal to zero and now all components of stiffness matrixes A and D can be

simplified as

$$A_{ij} = t\bar{Q}_{ij} \quad (8)$$

$$D_{ij} = \frac{t^3}{12}\bar{Q}_{ij} \quad (9)$$

Substituting the elastic constants into Eq. (8) and Eq. (9), the stiffness matrix of composite tape spring can be determined. Command **General shell stiffness* in ABAQUS is adopted to assign the section properties to tape spring, and meanwhile the local coordinate system is established to define fibre direction.

3 OPTIMIZATION

3.1 Analysis of mechanical properties

Figure 5 gives profiles of mechanical properties including moment and strain energy of composite tape spring in reverse folding and deploying processes. Compared to classical analytical moment variation, the two resultant moments have similar variation path. At initial stage of folding, moment linearly increases to a peak and then snaps to a smaller value due to buckling with increasing rotation, and finally moment stays an approximate constant till full folding. For moment in deploying process, it follows the inverse path of moment in folding process. It is obvious that from the enlarged plot the phenomenon of hysteresis appears as described in previous section.

For energy variation in Figure 5, it increases with increasing rotation, and the spike in folding process corresponds to the snap through at same rotation in moment curve. Similarly there is a hysteresis of energy in deploying process as clearly shown in the enlarged picture.

Figure 5: Mechanical properties of tape spring.

3.2 Multi-objective optimization

To obtain an optimal composite tape spring design, a multi-objective optimization is carried out with respect to geometric parameters. In literature [11], it can be found that even the composite tube hinge closely related to tape spring hinge has overshoot phenomenon in deployment process. This means that the single tape spring has high probability to overshoot, because the single tape has less stiffness compared to tube hinge. According to the mechanical properties analysis, the tape spring relies on strain energy and steady moment to

drive and on critical moment to lock. Considering the overshoot phenomenon, in other words, to obtain the good capacity of self-locking it must be specified a minimum value of critical moment, however the high critical moment means a huge external moment to rotate tape spring to buck, therefore the critical moment is limited less than a given value. In addition, the edges along length of tape spring are subjected to strong torsion, thus causing damage to composite materials; the longitudinal strain of tape spring is specified in a limit. In order to obtain a good driving ability, strain energy and steady moment should be high enough. In light of the analysis, we can obtain a multi-objective optimization model written as:

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \text{find } \mathbf{x} \in \mathbf{R}^n \\ \text{max } SM \\ \text{max } SE \\ \text{s.t. } \underline{C} \leq CM \leq \overline{C} \\ \varepsilon \leq \varepsilon_0 \\ \underline{x}_i \leq x_i \leq \overline{x}_i \end{array} \right. \quad (10)$$

where, \mathbf{x} represents design variables vector; \mathbf{R}^n is space of design variables; SE (strain energy) and SM (steady moment) are objectives, CM (critical moment) is constraint; $\overline{C}, \underline{C}$ represent upper and lower limits of constraint function of critical moment respectively; $\overline{x}_i, \underline{x}_i$ are upper and lower limits of design variables respectively; ε is longitudinal strain being of constraint.

For solving optimal model, the response surface methodology is firstly adopted to make the relationship explicit between objective as well as constraint functions and input variables. To ensure the precise of fitting polynomial, the sample points are designed with 2 factors of 5 levels each, corresponding responses and variable designs are given in Table 2, as follows:

Radius mm	Subtended angle °	CM N.mm	SM N.mm	SE mJ	LS %
14	90	184.234	34.9054	123.797	0.513
14	100	263.013	39.2653	142.53	0.553
14	110	368.303	43.9779	162.509	0.593
14	120	522.686	49.2367	184.309	0.662
14	130	734.283	55.3365	208.947	0.744
16	90	219.877	35.3846	125.708	0.474
16	100	320.723	40.347	145.181	0.522
16	110	467.305	46.0087	166.789	0.590
16	120	678.662	52.6943	191.689	0.688
16	130	992.175	60.32	221.361	0.800
18	90	257.974	36.4905	127.907	0.459
18	100	389.703	42.4195	148.956	0.537
18	110	589.981	49.3066	173.495	0.625
18	120	887.75	57.4498	203.112	0.745
18	130	1320.29	66.6691	239.81	0.891
20	90	308.019	38.4141	131.005	0.473

20	100	475.332	45.4364	154.565	0.568
20	110	747.138	53.6067	183.144	0.684
20	120	1150.74	63.0079	218.819	0.822
20	130	1678.48	70.4242	262.585	0.91
22	90	355.916	40.9652	135.374	0.502
22	100	590.136	49.0424	162.205	0.620
22	110	945.205	58.3464	195.774	0.748
22	120	1445.58	66.2316	237.296	0.842
22	130	2034.98	74.9746	284.535	0.943

Table 2: Sample points design.

Quadratic polynomial is selected to link functions and design variables, the obtained expressions based on MATLAB are written as:

$$SM = 435.9 - 37.07R - 5.35\theta + 1.10R^2 + 0.29R\theta + 0.03\theta^2 - 0.01R^3 - 0.004R^2\theta - 0.0004R\theta^2 - 4.4 \cdot 10^{-5}\theta^3 \quad (11)$$

$$SE = 600.7 + 34.85R + 15.84\theta - 0.03R^2 - 0.85R\theta - 0.09\theta^2 - 0.01R^3 + 0.009R^2\theta + 0.003R\theta^2 + 0.0002\theta^3 \quad (12)$$

$$CM = -7034 + 463R + 182.8\theta - 0.97R^2 + 11.48R\theta - 1.25\theta^2 - 0.13R^3 + 0.1R^2\theta + 0.05R\theta^2 + 0.002\theta^3 \quad (13)$$

$$\varepsilon = 13.5 - 1.26R - 0.16\theta + 0.04R^2 + 0.009R\theta + 0.0007\theta^2 - 0.0004R^3 - 0.0001R^2\theta - 1.83 \cdot 10^{-5}R\theta^2 - 8.68 \cdot 10^{-7}\theta^3 \quad (14)$$

For multi-objective optimization, the modified Non-Dominated Sorting Genetic Algorithm (ASGA-II) is utilized to solve optimal model, according to results of tube hinge in [15], tape spring in this paper is required to reach the mechanical properties of tube hinge, therefore, the resultant moments in the literature are constraints in this paper and the upper limit of strain here is half the result obtained in the literature. After convergence, an optimal design is selected among all Pareto solutions according to the maximum steady moment, as listed in Table 2. Meanwhile the optimal design is modelled and simulated, we obtain the mechanical properties in Table 3, and it is obvious that the differences are all less than 1%, which indicates the results in optimization is accurate.

	constraints of CM	constraints of ε
Constraints configurations	lower limit: 414 N.mm upper limit: 1337 N.mm	< 0.75%
	radius	subtended angle
Optimal design	16.16 mm	125.5°

Table 3: Results from optimization.

Methods	CM / N.mm	SM / N.mm	SM / N.mm	ε
Optimization	869.4	208.9	57.6	0.75
Simulation	868.797	207.816	56.677	0.7509

Table 4: Verification for optimal design.

4 CONCLUSIONS

This paper deals with a multi-objective optimization for composite tape spring. The equivalent elastic constants are obtained from a plain weave representative unit cell based on TexGen4SC, and according to classical laminated plate theory, ABD matrix is calculated. Mechanical properties exhibiting in folding process of tape spring are investigated, and based on this an optimization with respect to geometric parameters is carried out. The final optimal design is radius of 16.16 mm and subtended angle of 125.5° , meanwhile the design is modelled and simulated, results show that the two solutions have differences being less than 1%; it implies that the optimal design is accurate. The whole optimization process presents a reference for design of composite tape spring.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The project is supported by the National Natural Science Foundation of China (11072009), Beijing Education Committee Development Project (SQKM201610005001) and Beijing University of Technology Basic Research Fund (001000514313003).

REFERENCES

- [1] W. Wuest. Einige anwendungen der theorie der zylinderschale. *Zamm Journal of Applied Mathematics & Mechanics Zeitschrift Für Angewandte Mathematik Und Mechanik*, 1954, 34(12):444–454.
- [2] E.H. Mansfield. Large-deflexion torsion and flexure of initially curved strips. *Proceedings of the Royal Society A Mathematical Physical & Engineering Sciences*, 1973, 334(1598):279-298.
- [3] K.A. Seffen, You Z, S. Pellegrino (2000) Folding and deployment of curved tape-springs. *International Journal of Mechanical Sciences*, 42(10), 2055-2073.
- [4] K.A. Seffen (2001) On the behavior of folded tape-springs. *Journal of Applied Mechanics*, 68(3), 369-375.
- [5] S. Bourgeois, B. Cochelin, F. Guinot, E. Picault. Buckling analysis of tape-springs using a rod model with flexible cross-sections. *European Journal of Computational Mechanics/Revue Européenne de Mécanique Numérique*, 2012, 21(3-6), 184-194.
- [6] F. Guinot, S. Bourgeois, B. Cochelin, L. Blanchard. A planar rod model with flexible thin-walled cross-sections. Application to the folding of tape-springs. *International Journal of Solids and Structures*, 2012, 49(1), 73-86.
- [7] S.J.I. Walker, G.S Aglietti. A Study into the dynamics of three dimensional tape spring folds. *Aiaa Journal*, 2004, 42(4):850-856.
- [8] S.J.I. Walker, G.S. Aglietti. Experimental investigation of tape springs folded in three dimensions. *Aiaa Journal*, 2006, 44(1):151-159.
- [9] F. Dewalque, J.P. Collette, O. Brüls Mechanical behaviour of tape-springs used in the deployment of reflectors around a solar panel. *Acta Astronautica*, 2015, 123: 271-282.

- [10] J.C. Yee, S. Pellegrino. Composite tube hinges. *Journal of Aerospace Engineering*, 2005, 18(4), 224-231.
- [11] H.M.Y.C. Mallikarachchi, S. Pellegrino Quasi-static folding and deployment of ultrathin composite tape-spring hinges. *Journal of Spacecraft and Rockets*, 2011, 48(1), 187-198.
- [12] L. Xin, Y. Wenbin (2017), "TexGen4SC," <https://cdmhub.org/resources/texgen4sc>.
- [13] L. Hua., L.P. Brown, A.C. Long. Modelling and simulating textile structures using TexGen. *In Advanced Materials Research*, 2011, 331: pp. 44-47.
- [14] Y. Hongling, Z. Chunhua, Z. Yang, Y. Qi, X. Yanni. Analysis of mechanical properties in bending processes and optimal design of simple tape spring. *Journal of Modeling in Mechanics and Materials*, 2017, doi:10.1515/jmmm-2016-0156.
- [15] Y. Hui, L. Rongqiang, W. Yan, D. Zongquan, G. Hongwei. Experiment and multi-objective optimization design of tape-spring hinges. *Structural and Multidisciplinary Optimization*, 2015, 51(6), 1373-1384.